

**ЮМШОҚ БУҒДОЙНИНГ ҲОСИЛДОРЛИГИГА
ТАШҚИ – МУҲИТНИНГ ТАЪСИРИ.**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7115048>

Introduction. In ensuring of food stuff safety, spicate cereal crops, including increase of soft wheat yielding capacity and quality is considered as one of the most significant tasks of grain growing nowadays. Introduction of new high quality and at the same time possessing by such properties as stable productivity, adaptation to natural factors, ecologic plasticity and technologic advantages are required in agricultural production. In modern selection adoption of cost-effective, adaptive, resistant to diseases and with high quality grain variety give possibility to increase of ecologic and economic level of agriculture, strengthen cereal productivity [1].

Academician A.A.Zhuchenko [2] emphasized that one of the main criterions, under the influence of abiotic and biotic factors, is generalized valuation of seed growing and varieties approbation, providing constant quality of high productivity and yielding capacity. In various ecologic conditions, possessing by wide homeostatism, changeability and adaptability of the variety, ensure plant stability and at the same time high cropping power (3). As a result of study of wheat species adaptation to environmental conditions, it was defined that the harvest quantity and species susceptibility to stress factors are independent components of general adaptation [4]. The main object of the scientific research is in exploration of agrobiologic characteristics of collection specimens of autumn soft wheat, definition of variety ecologic plasticity, mutual influence of outer environment and genotypes, having constant productive level.

Materials and methods of the research. Experiments in 2016-2018 were conducted on the fields of Durmon experimental plot of Genetics and experimental biology of plants institute of ASRUz situating in Kibray district, Tashkent region. Relative humidity of the place of experiment conducting is unstable (changeable) in March-June months hydrothermal coefficient (HTC) is equal to 1.57 ha. Average temperature is 19.7⁰C, observing temperature is 21.3⁰C (average of March-June months) observed and on comparison with average was more for 1.74⁰C.

Serving as source of the research CIMMYT from gene pool of international organization of the 46-th IBWSN (from selected nursery of international soft wheat), 200 samples were used, specimens were planted on the plot with 1m²area in three repetitions by randomization method during three years, yield stability, soil adaptation to climatic conditions and ecologic plasticity were

studied. Indexes of ecologic plasticity (bi-regression coefficient) and stability (S_i^2 - standard deviation) were conducted by E.A.Eberkhart and V.A.Rassel (5) by using method of V.Z.Pakudina and L.M.Lopatina (6).

The results of the research. Adaptation and stability of collection specimens' productivity to soil-climatic conditions, genotypes plasticity in unfavorable conditions were estimated during the experiment. Ten samples, possessing by high grain productivity, were selected from studied samples and statistically processed. Adaptation of wheat variety to the environmental conditions initially passed experimental tests and implemented into production, as the most significant characteristics of varieties, they were evaluated by their plasticity and productive stability. In estimating productive stability of studied collection samples and genotypes ecologic plasticity on years, regression coefficient (b_i), based on estimation of linear regression coefficient and stability coefficient, was used.

First of all, for calculation of regression coefficient (b_i), index of environmental condition is defined. Indicator of environmental condition can be positive and negative. Good development and productivity increase of varieties is expressed by positive value of ecologic index, or on the contrary by negative value (table-1). On experiment results of 2016 ($i_j=0.4$, 2018 ($i_j=0.5$) positive conditions, and in 2017 ($i_j=1.0$) negative conditions were observed. Regression coefficient b_i exercises influence on grades and their productivity in changeable environmental conditions. How high coefficient $b_i > 1$, so it can be subjected to environmental conditions, that is ecologic plasticity property can be low, such sorts require high farming practices. If $b_i < 1$ lower, causing less influence as regards to changes in environmental conditions, then it is considered that plasticity properties are high. It can be used low level of farming practices in such grades.

In our research works in specimens with catalogue number 1125 and 1251 ecologic plasticity ($b_i > 0.9$) was on high level and close to them indexes were observed in samples with catalogue numbers 1289 (1.0); 1131 (1.0); 1088 (1.0); 1006 (1.0) and 1164 (1.0) (table-1). In the rest samples 1296 (1.1); 1082 (1.1) and 1136 (1.1) regression coefficient suddenly became high, defining that these specimens belong to varieties of intensive type and to obtain high yield from these grades, by means of conducting great farming practices, they can be adapted to environmental conditions. From theoretical point of view, how little the index of standard deviation (S_i^2), so stable varieties adaptation to environmental conditions. In our research work, when analyzing samples

productivity index during years, all samples stability on years was observed. However, among specimens relatively the lowest index on relative stability property observed in 1006 (0.21); 1164 (0.73); 1136 (0.46); 1251 (0.50); 1131 (0.71) and 1296 (0.80) specimens. It was defined that these samples on relation to environmental conditions during years did not lose their stability property. In the rest 1289 (1.044); 1125 (1.18); 1088 (1.308) and 1082 (1.05) samples were estimated on relative intermediate calculations. Variation coefficient (V%) is a relative unit of measurement of quantitative variation. If variation coefficient is till 10%, then changeability is insignificant, if on average 10-20%, or more than

Table-1

Yield, ecologic plasticity, stability and changeability of yield indexes of collection nursery

Catalogue number	Productivity t/ha			ΣY_i	Y_i	Ecologic plasticity b_i	stability S_i^2	V%
	2016	2017	2018					
1296	6,9	5,3	6,2	18,4	6,13	1,1	0,80	13,08
1289	7,1	5,4	7,3	19,8	6,60	1,0	1,04	15,82
1131	7,3	6,03	7,2	20,53	6,80	1,0	0,71	10,32
1125	8,1	6,1	8,2	22,4	7,47	0,9	1,18	15,87
1088	8,1	5,5	7,06	20,66	6,88	1,0	1,31	19,0
1251	7,5	6,9	7,9	21,7	7,49	0,9	0,50	6,77
1082	6,2	5,2	7,3	18,7	6,23	1,1	1,05	16,85
1136	6,0	5,4	6,3	17,72	5,90	1,1	0,46	7,80
1006	6,8	6,4	6,7	19,9	6,63	1,0	0,21	3,14
1164	6,0	5,7	7,1	18,83	6,27	1,1	0,73	11,66
Mean Y_j	7,0	5,8	7,1	19,7	6,6			
ΣY_i	70,05	57,93	71,26	199,2	66,0			
I_j	0,4	-1,0	0,5					
LCD 0,5	1,06т/га							

20% it is considered as significant. In the research the lowest index in samples with catalogue number 1006 (3.14%); 1136 (7.8%) and 1251 (6.77%) in the rest specimens average variability was observed.

Conclusions

On abovementioned results, the highest index of productivity on years was observed in specimen with catalogue number 1251, sample 1125 was on the next place. It was observed that these samples possessing by high plasticity and

stability characteristic from genetic point of view, differ from other specimens by their adaptability to environmental conditions. These samples were selected and recommended to employment in the selection process. In the selection process is significant to pay attention to the fact that these characteristics occupy important place.

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